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Perceived Environmental And Health Effects Of Illegal Oil Bunkering In The South-South Region Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Illegal oil bunkering is an unhealthy practice that poses health and environmental challenges to the inhabitants that are exposed to it. This study investigated the perceived environmental and health effects of illegal oil bunkering in the South-South Region of Nigeria. The descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted with a population consisting of all adult residents in the region. The sample size was 400. The purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Illegal Oil Bunkering Environmental and Health Problem Questionnaire (IOBEaHPQ)” with a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data collection was done by a face to face delivery of the questionnaire to the respondents. and analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 27.0 using mean and standard deviation. The result showed that the environment problems of oil bunkering are: black soot (3.78 ± 0.40), residents’ means of livelihood like fishing and farming in the environment is not thriving any longer (3.67 ± 0.48), fire accident which damages properties (3.65 ± 0.55), bunkering activities have contaminated the soil which affects plants (3.57 ± 0.49), and increased heat, hotness of the weather due to oil bunkering (3.29 ± 0.45). The result showed that the perceived physical health problems were: air pollution which affects the lungs (3.99 ± 0.14) and causes breathing difficulties (3.47 ± 0.49), burnt injuries (3.50 ± 0.50); mental health problems were: increased stress and anxiety among the youths (3.51 ± 0.51), loss of interest in education because of the distractions from oil bunkering activities (3.14 ± 1.31), and loss of concentration among residents because of disturbance from bunkering activities (2.99 ± 0.11); social health problems were: delinquent behaviour (3.74 ± 0.49), aggressive behaviour (3.58 ± 0.70), smoking and alcoholism (3.55 ± 0.51), cultism or fraternity associations (3.17 ± 0.83), and loss of loved ones to bunkering (2.95 ± 0.68). It was concluded that, illegal oil bunkering is not without environmental and health problems wherever is practiced. The most prominent environment problem been black sooth and air pollution which in turn affects health negatively in all dimension. It was recommended among others that the law enforcement agencies should curb oil bunkering by putting more force to prosecute anyone who is dealing on illegal oil theft. Also, environmental agencies should also monitor the activities of illegal oil theft by implementing strict environmental laws that will minimize such activities.

Keywords: Bunkering, Environment, Effect, Health, South-South Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of oil bunkering has often been discussed from the social, and economic viewpoints, but not much has been said about it from the perspective of environmental and health standpoint. It is well known that environmental pollution is a huge problem in the South-South Region of Nigeria. In large swathes of the region, air, land and water qualities are not anything close to being healthy, as a result of oil activities. Due to oil spillage, the soil is no longer arable for farming, and the rivers cannot sustain fishes nor produce clean water for drinking. Environmental pollution has deprived many communities in the Niger Delta of their means of livelihood with many of the locals saying that they can no longer engage in their fishing and farming occupations (Favour, 2020). He further stated that there is abundant evidence that oil bunkering has created even far more environmental damages in the region, causing unusual temperature levels and the introduction of soot, mostly black soot.

Bunkering is the supplying of fuel for use by ships (such fuel is referred to as bunker), including the logistics of loading and distributing the fuel among available shipboard tanks. A person dealing in trade of bunker (fuel) is called a bunker trader. The term bunkering originated in the days of steamships, when coal was stored in bunkers. Nowadays, the term bunker is generally applied to the petroleum products stored in tanks, and bunkering to the practice and business of refueling ships. Bunkering operations take place at seaports and include the storage and provision of the bunker (ship fuels) to vessels. In countries such as Nigeria, "bunkering" also refers to the clandestine siphoning off or diverting of oil from pipelines and storage facilities. Such bunkering is often crudely carried out, causing both accidents and pollution (Manaadiar, 2016).

Oil theft and illegal bunkering can be used interchangeably as one may lead to the other. Oil theft is the illegal taking away of oil by whatever means and diverting it for personal gain (Adishi & Hunga 2017). Illegal bunkering is the act of hacking into pipelines to steal crude oil which is later refined or sold abroad (Ugwuanyi, 2013). Illegal bunkering as oil taken from pipelines or flow stations, as well as extra crude oil added to legitimate cargo that is not accounted for. Oil bunkering is the most common form of oil theft that includes direct tapping of oil, breaking or vandalizing pipelines, fuel scooping, illegal refining among others (Odalonu, 2015).

Some South-South communities admit their role in the theft of oil but blame continuing poverty and pollution for their actions (Ngwogwugwu et al, 2012). Therefore, it is seen as a legitimate business (Adishi & Hunga 2017). According to Odalonu (2015), it is believed that the reason, oil theft or illegal bunkering continue to thrive in Nigeria despite the efforts of the government is because the political class is benefiting from it. Illegal bunkering is not for the poor. The actors of oil bunkering are people who can afford to hire tankers and barges, (Dominic, 2016). Presently, these illegal acts in the Niger Delta involves a complex web of relationship spanning across the society, (Adishi & Hunga, 2017). This include people of diverse interest such as highly connected people in and outside government (members of the executive and legislative arms of government), oil companies including Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), businessmen, retired and serving military officers, and militants among others (Ayanruoh, 2013). The main players involved in these illegal business are at various level.

Human health and well-being are intimately linked to the state of the environment. Good quality natural environments provide basic needs, in terms of clean air and water, fertile land for food production, and energy and material inputs for production. Green infrastructure also serves to regulate climate and prevent flooding. Access to green and blue spaces also provides important opportunities for recreation and supports well-being. At the same time, the environment represents an important pathway for human exposure to polluted air, noise and hazardous chemicals. In their report on preventing disease through healthy environments, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that environmental stressors are responsible for 12–18 % of all deaths in the 53 countries of the WHO Europe Region. Improving the quality of the environment in key areas such as air, water and noise can prevent disease and improve human health (WHO, 2016). Air pollution is a prominent environmental health risk in illegal oil bunkering.

Environmental degradation of the aquatic system is pronounced as reported by Odalonu (2015) that, despite community concern about the quality of fish, the accumulation of hydrocarbons in fish is not a

serious issue in the region but the fisheries sector is suffering due to the destruction of fish habitat in the mangroves. More worrisome is the fact that, the persons involved in the bunkering activities are not left out in the effects, as some of them have had severe burns, maltreatment from security personnel, damages or economic loss to their equipment yet, they still continue in it, particularly in the Rivers State, where most of the country's oil wells are located, and are mostly in places surrounded by water and mangroves; so, their oil tanks and siphoning points are mostly hidden in the mangroves but, the effects of their activities are always visible as the rivers have turned black with spilled oil floating all over the waters. This causes a health and environmental threat to aquatic lives including that of humans who consume the fishes affected. More visible, is the soot that is highly prevalent in the area causing air pollution and health threat. There is the possibility that if the health and environmental problems associated with oil bunkering is brought to the lime light, it may give a pointer to what actions should be taken to curb the menace. The study provided answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the perceived environment effects of illegal oil bunkering in the South-South Region of Nigeria?
2. What are the perceived physical health effects of illegal oil bunkering in the South-South Region of Nigeria?
3. What are the perceived mental health effects of illegal oil bunkering in the South-South Region of Nigeria?
4. What are the perceived social effects of illegal oil bunkering in the South-South Region of Nigeria?

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in South-South Nigeria, precisely Rivers State which hosts most of the country's oil wells. The descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted with a population consisting of all adult residents in the region. The sample size for the study was 400, which was determined using the Taro Yamane formula – $n = N/1 + N(e)^2$; where n = sample size, N = population of the study estimated to be (709,112) and e = margin of error set at 0.05. The purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Illegal Oil Bunkering Environmental and Health Problem Questionnaire (IOBEaHPQ)". The instrument was validated by three experts and had a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data collection was done by a face to face delivery of the questionnaire to the respondents. The data analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 27.0 using mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS

The results of the study are shown below:

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the environmental problems of oil bunkering in South-South, Nigeria (N = 400)

SN	Environmental problems of oil bunkering	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	Soot is everywhere in the environment because of oil bunkering	3.78	0.40
2	Bunkering activities lead to fire accident which damages properties	3.67	0.55
3	Bunkering activities have contaminated the soil which affects plants	3.56	0.49
4	Oil bunkering contaminated the rivers and fishes no longer survive	3.42	0.74
5	The beauty of our natural environment is destroyed because of oil bunkering	3.12	0.64
6	The mangroves are destroyed by oil bunkering	3.01	0.72
7	There is increases heat, hotness of the weather due to oil bunkering	3.28	0.45
8	Residents are exposed to fire accident due to oil bunkering	3.14	0.39
9	Residents' means of livelihood like fishing and farming in the environment is not thriving any longer	3.68	0.48
10	Activities of oil bunkering reduces the environmental quality	3.46	0.58
Grand mean		3.41	0.54

Criterion mean = 2.50. Key: SHP = Social health problem; NSHP = not a social health problem

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation on environmental problems of oil bunkering. The result showed that the environment problems of oil bunkering are: black soot everywhere in the environment (3.78 ± 0.40), residents' means of livelihood like fishing and farming in the environment is not thriving any longer (3.67 ± 0.48), bunkering activities lead to fire accident which damages properties (3.65 ± 0.55), bunkering activities have contaminated the soil which affects plants (3.57 ± 0.49), activities of oil bunkering reduces the environmental quality (3.47 ± 0.58), oil bunkering contaminated the rivers and fishes no longer survive (3.41 ± 0.74), and increased heat, hotness of the weather due to oil bunkering (3.29 ± 0.45).

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the perceived physical health problems of oil bunkering in South-South Nigeria (N = 400)

SN	Perceived Physical health problems of oil bunkering	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	Oil bunkering leads to air pollution which affects the lungs	3.98	0.14
2	Oil bunkering leads to air pollution which causes breathing difficulties	3.46	0.49
3	It increases the risk of asthma	3.29	0.44
4	Inhalation of soot arising from bunkering activities is very dangerous to human health	3.51	0.49
5	Bunkering activities affects the skin of the residents	3.57	0.49
6	Oil bunkering reduces the air quality which humans breath	3.24	0.43
7	Oil bunkering impact the immune system of residents as they inhale the emissions in the environment	3.44	0.49
8	Many residents are presented with respiratory diseases because of oil bunkering in the area	3.73	0.44
9	There are complains about heart, or cardiovascular diseases because of the consistent oil bunkering activities	2.95	0.30
10	Several bunt injuries in the area is caused by oil bunkering	3.51	0.50
Grand mean		3.46	0.42

Criterion mean = 2.50.

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation on the perceived physical health problems of oil bunkering. The result showed that the perceived physical health problems of oil bunkering are: air pollution which affects the lungs (3.98 ± 0.14) and causes breathing difficulties (3.46 ± 0.49), respiratory diseases (3.73 ± 0.44), skin diseases (3.57 ± 0.49), inhalation of soot (3.51 ± 0.49), burnt injuries (3.51 ± 0.50), and cardiovascular diseases (2.95 ± 0.30).

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the perceived mental health problems of oil bunkering in South-South Nigeria (N = 400)

SN	Perceived Mental health problems of oil bunkering	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	There is reduced intelligence among the youths because oil bunkering which have captured their mind	2.78	0.52
2	Children have learning difficulties because of the distractions they get from oil bunkering activities	3.40	0.50
3	Depression is linked to oil bunkering	2.76	1.11
4	There is loss of concentration among residents because of disturbance from bunkering activities	2.99	0.11
5	Oil bunkering increases stress and anxiety among the youths	3.51	0.51
6	Mood swing is observed in the residents due to oil bunkering activities which pollutes the environment	3.02	0.75
7	Oil bunkering activities causes distraction from mental work	3.28	0.47
8	Oil bunkering activities makes studying difficult for the residents	3.28	0.86
9	The residents may not have any interest in education because of the distractions from oil bunkering activities	3.14	1.31
10	Psychological abuse is observed in the area due to oil bunkering	2.72	0.45
Grand mean		3.08	.65

Criterion mean = 2.50.

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation on perceived mental health problems of oil bunkering in South-South Nigeria. The result showed that the perceived mental health problems of oil bunkering are: increased stress and anxiety among the youths (3.51 ± 0.51) followed by learning difficulties because of the distractions they get from oil bunkering activities (3.40 ± 0.50), distraction from mental work (3.28 ± 0.47), difficulty in studying (3.28 ± 0.86), loss of interest in education because of the distractions from oil bunkering activities (3.14 ± 1.31), mood swing in residents due to oil bunkering activities which pollutes the environment (3.02 ± 0.75), and loss of concentration among residents because of disturbance from bunkering activities (2.99 ± 0.11).

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation on the perceived social health problems of oil bunkering in South-South Nigeria (N = 400)

SN	Perceived Social health problems of oil bunkering	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	The youths are exhibiting aggressive behaviour because of the oil bunkering activities in the area	3.58	0.70
2	Delinquent behaviour has become the order of the day due to oil bunkering	3.74	0.49
3	Children and youths no long respect their parents and elders	3.48	0.55
4	Family relationships have now become unstable due to bunkering	3.20	0.53
5	Physical and sexual assault has become rampant	3.46	0.60
6	Smoking and alcoholism can be linked to oil bunkering	3.55	0.51
7	Families loss their loved ones to bunkering activities	2.95	0.68
8	The high prevalence of cultism or fraternity associations is due to oil bunkering activities	3.17	0.83
9	Parents no longer have control over their children or wards	2.52	0.91
10	Violent behaviours in the society is traceable to oil bunkering	3.46	0.59
Grand mean		3.31	0.63

Criterion mean = 2.50.

Table 4 presents the mean and standard deviation on perceived social health problems of oil bunkering in South-South Nigeria. The result showed that the perceived social health problems of oil bunkering are: delinquent behaviour (3.74±0.49) followed by aggressive behaviour (3.58±0.70), smoking and alcoholism (3.55±0.51), violent behaviour (3.46±0.59) physical and sexual assault (3.46±0.60), cultism or fraternity associations (3.17±0.83), and loss of loved ones to bunkering (2.95±0.68).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study were discussed below:

The result showed that the environmental problems of oil bunkering are: soot, disruption of means of livelihood like fishing and farming, fire accident which damages properties, contamination of soil and rivers, reduction of environmental quality, and increased heat, hotness of the weather due to oil bunkering. The finding of this study agrees with that of Ogbija et al. (2015) whose study on the effects of environmental degradation on human health in selected oil communities in Delta State showed that environmental degradation by human activities such as oil bunkering is linked to environmental degradation; in all, 77.5% of the residents in oil producing communities were vulnerable to environmental degradation. The implication of this high vulnerability to environmental degradation by the people of these oil producing communities in Delta State shows that something must be done urgently to make living condition better in these areas for them to be resilient to oil activities.

The findings of this study showed that the perceived physical health problems of oil bunkering are: air pollution which affects the lungs and causes breathing difficulties, respiratory diseases, skin diseases, inhalation of soot, burnt injuries, and cardiovascular diseases. The finding of this study is anticipated because even physical evidence shows soot everywhere which is inhaled, turning human nose to black most of the times and making breathing difficult sometimes. The finding of this study is in consonance with that of Brook et al. (2010) which revealed that such activities leading to air pollution brought about reduced lung function. The finding of this study is also in agreement with the studies of Katholi and Couri (2011), and Leary et al. (2014) which showed that the effects of any activity including illegal bunkering which give rise to air pollution can be enormous and ranges from simple discomfort, such as irritation of the eyes, nose, skin, throat, wheezing, coughing and chest tightness, and breathing difficulties, to more serious states, such as lung and heart problems to headaches. Also, the findings of this study is in line

with that of Filleul et al. (2005) who reported associations between increased respiratory and cardiovascular morbidity as a result of exposures to particulate particles arising from air pollution due to oil bunkering activities. The similarity between the present study and the previous ones might be due to the similar design used, as they both adopted the descriptive research design to unveil the health problems of illegal oil bunkering. The finding of this study differs from that of Ordinioha and Sawyer (2010) which showed that the physical health problems of crude oil spill in a rural community in Bayelsa State was diarrhea, sore eyes and itchy skin. This difference could be because of the present study was not specific about the physical health problems highlighted by Ordinioha and colleague.

The result revealed that the perceived mental health problems of oil bunkering are: increased stress and anxiety among the youths, followed by learning difficulties, difficulty in studying, mood swing, and loss of concentration. This finding is also presumed because in our society today, many youths have preferred making quick money rather than exercising their mental abilities to generate idea or concentrate on studies that will exposed them to several information that may transform their lives better than illegal oil bunkering. The finding of this study is in keeping with that of Kessler and Brome (2013) which showed that air pollution which is caused mainly by oil bunkering has also been correlated with depression, a serious mental disorder affecting people exposed to it. The finding is in accordance with the result of Jerome et al (2016) that many respondents indicated high mental distress. The finding of this study also agrees with that of Torres and Casey (2017) which showed that, exposure to such activities results in a variety of problems such as stress, depression, anxiety, irritation, becoming short-tempered, and mood swings. The finding of this study is also in consonance with that of Fisch et al. (2003) which showed that which associated such activities with low mood. The similarity between the previous studies and the present one could be due to the fact that anywhere oil bunkering activities exists, the effects produced are always the same due to the similar exposure of people to the hazards that emanate from such activities.

The finding of the study showed that the perceived social health problems of oil bunkering are: delinquent behaviour, aggressive behaviour, smoking and alcoholism, violent behaviour, physical and sexual assault, cultism or fraternity associations and loss of loved ones to fire outbreak during bunkering. This finding is envisaged because of the increasing rate of such deviant behaviours among our youths of which one of the major factors is illegal oil bunkering. The finding of this study support other studies such as Lim et al (2012) and Calderon-Garciduenas et al. (2015) which show a positive correlation between such activities and deviant human behaviour. The finding of this study also corroborates the report of the World Health Organization (2012) which reported the effect of air pollution arising also from oil bunkering on changes in sexual behaviour. The finding of this study agrees with that of Torres and Casey (2017) which showed that, exposure to polluted air results in a variety of problems which adversely affect behaviour. The similarity of the study terrain could be implicated for the similarity found between the previous study and the present one. The finding of this study aligns with that of Ordinioha and Sawyer (2010) which showed that the social health problems of crude oil spill in a rural community in Bayelsa State was cigarette smoking.

CONCLUSION

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that, illegal oil bunkering is not without environmental and health problems wherever is practiced. The most prominent environment problem been black sooth and air pollution which in turn affects health negatively in all dimension.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were put forward based on the findings of the study:

1. The law enforcement agencies should curb oil bunkering by putting more force to prosecute anyone who is dealing on illegal oil theft.
2. Environmental agencies should also monitor the activities of illegal oil theft by implementing strict environmental laws that will minimize such activities.
3. The National Oil Spill Detection Response Agency should protect the residents from the effects of oil bunkering by mapping out better strategies to minimize such operations.

4. The Federal Government through the Federal Ministry of Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) should protect the environment by deploying more military personnel to guide the oil pipelines.
5. The Niger Delta Affairs Ministry should make health condition better in these areas by sending health team to carry out a comprehensive health outreach at the areas affected by oil bunkering from time to time.

REFERENCES

- Adishi, E., & Hunga, M. O. (2015). *Oil theft impact on Nigeria economy*. Hunga.
- Ayanruoh, F. (2013). *Oil and Gas: A serious environmental protection proposal*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com> › Business › Energy
- Brook, R. D., Rajagopalan, S., Pope, C. A., I. I. I., Brook, J. R., Bhatnagar, A. & Diez-Roux, A. V. (2010). Particulate Matter air pollution and cardiovascular disease. An update to the Scientific Statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*, 121(21), 2331–2378.
- Calderon-Garciduenas, L., Calderon-Garciduenas, A., Torres-Jardon, R., Avila-Ramirez, J., Kulesza, R.J. & Angiulli, A.D. (2015). Air pollution and your brain: what do you need to know right now. *Primary Health Care Research and Development*, 16(4), 329-345.
- Favour, C.M. (2020). Climate, NDC and the problem of oil bunkering in Nigeria. *Health Affairs*, 30(5), 879-887.
- Filleul, L., Rondeau, V., Vandentorren, S., Le Moual, N., Cantagrel, A. & Annesi-Maesano, I. (2005). Twenty-five year mortality and air pollution: Results from the French PAARC survey. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 62(7), 453–460.
- Fisch, H., Andrews, H.F., Fisch, K.S., Golden, R., Liberson, G., & Olsson, C.A. (2003). The relationship of long term global temperature change and human fertility. *Medical Hypotheses*, 61(1), 21-28.
- Jerome, N., Emilia, A. U., Ibang, E., & Godwin E. (2016). Health risks associated with oil pollution in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 4(9), 122-132.
- Katholi, R.E., & Couri, D.M. (2011). Left ventricular hypertrophy: major risk factor in patients with hypertension: update and practical clinical applications. *International Journal of Hypertension*, <https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/495349>
- Kessler, R.C. & Bromet, E.J. (2013). The epidemiology of depression across cultures. *Annual Reviews Public Health*, 34, 119-138.
- Manaadiar, M. (2016). Navy raids oil bunkering operations. <https://saharareporters.com> › 2016/09/05 › navy-raids-
- Ngwogwugwu, N., Emmanuel, C. A. O., & Egwuonwu, O. (2012). Militancy and insecurity in Niger Delta, impact on the inflow of foreign direct investment to Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 2(1), 23-37
- Ordinioha, B., & Sawyer, W. (2010). Acute health effects of a crude oil spill in a rural community Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*, 19, 140 – 144.
- Odalonu, H. B. (2015). The upsurge of Oil Theft and Illegal Bunkering in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria: is there a way out? Center for population and Environmental Development, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences (MCSE) Publishing, Rome-Italy*, 352, 1-7.
- Ogbija, T. E., Atubi, A.O., & Ojeh, V. N. (2015). Effects of Environmental Degradation on Human Health in Selected Oil Communities in Delta State. Department of Geography and Regional Planning, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 5(9), www.iiste.org
- Torres, J. M., & Casey, J.A. (2017). The centrality of social ties to climate migration and mental health. *BMC Public Health*, 17(1), 600-607.
- Ugwuanyi, E. (2013). *Oil theft: Endless Search*. Solution the Nation.
- World Health Organization (2016). *Oil bunkering regional report*. WHO.
- World Health Organisation (2012). *Health effects of black carbon*. WHO.